

BM5102 ORGANIZATIONAL BEHAVIOUR

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Reflective Critique Report

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Before pursuing Master of Management

The basis for a manager's job is to help an organization achieve a high performance by best utilizing its people and material resources (Schemerhorn, 2013). However, managing people is not an easy task. Therefore, managers need to utilize their managerial skills in accomplishing their duties and these skills affect the efficiency of their work (Papulová and Mokroš, 2007). Such managerial skills can be gained by training or learning. A competent manager is not only a critical asset for a company but possessing these skills also offer competitive advantage for individuals. Therefore, by pursuing a Master degree in Management, my main goal is to improve my skills and knowledge on management through learning. I was motivated to know more about the theories behind management as I have always been fond of learning. I personally believe that by the end of this journey, I will acquire a valuable understanding and skills of the course as I hope to pursue a career in management and to apply what I have gained from this experience. Thus, this report will discuss my experience and reflection as a student of the module *BM5102 Organizational Behaviour*. However, due to the current pandemic, this module has been changed to a 100% coursework assessment where we were given two research projects; A group case study project (presentation and report) and an Individual Assessment (IA) analysis paper, a weekly online discussion, a reflective critique paper as well as an online midterm test.

During the journey

During the start of the module, I learned briefly about the basics of organizational behaviour. According to Judge and Robbins (2013), *Organizational Behaviour* is the study of human behaviour in the workplace and the effect of behaviour on organizational performance. One of the first assignments given for this module was regarding the topic of *personality, individual differences* and *mental ability*. The task required us to connect the importance of the three aspects within a global company of our choice. It was challenging at the beginning, as the lecture has not started and the topic was fairly new to me, but it did help me to see the significance of the said facets for organizations to grow and perform well. From my research for this assignment, I found that Lenovo assesses and utilizes personality, mental ability and individual differences as part of their company growth strategy, to promote diversity, innovation, job performance and recognition of talent (Lenovo, 2020). Recruitment and selection process is important for organization because if it is done right, it helps boost retention and benefits them holistically. In contrast, hiring the *wrong* person is not only costly, but a waste of time as well as effort (Acton, 2016). With the knowledge I have gained by doing this particular assignment, it has also made me reflect back on my recent experience in recruiting and selecting employees for the company that I am currently working for. I personally believe that this insight is important to have especially for a small medium enterprise that could not afford big losses. Wistfully, we did not receive feedback for this assignment from the lecturer as according to Hattie and Timperley (2007) feedback is known to have a compelling impact on learning.

Another assignment that has left an impact to me is the group case study project where we were asked to collect primary data. The topic for the group case study assignment was chosen from a list of 26 different titles; '*Issues and challenges on Halal education, training and development in Brunei*'. The goal for this research was to provide an overview of the local Halal industry and to investigate the issues and challenges faced by the different stakeholders

pertaining to the Halal education, training and development. The data collection was to be made through semi-structured face-to-face interviews with three main organizations in the Halal field namely Universiti Sultan Sharif Ali (UNISSA), Bahagian Kawalan Makanan Halal department under the Ministry of Religious Affairs and Ghanim International Corporation. The questions to be asked were also tied back to the topics under the module, specifically on employee motivation and its effect on organization's effectiveness (Robbins and Judge, 2013). After determining the issues, comparisons were to be made with Halal industries from neighbouring countries, namely Malaysia, Indonesia and Singapore to see any similarities in issues and challenges faced thus analysing the applicability of the solutions made to overcome them. The data were to be gathered from published journals, articles and research reports from various academic sources.

The final presentation for the case study project was set on the 7th week after the assignment was given to us and as for the report, it was to be submitted the following week. In the first week, my group and I completed a literature review table for our topic and we managed to obtain various Halal-related articles that focus on issues and challenges. Subsequently, we handed in our sets of questions for the interview along with our research permission form in the second week with the approval from our lecturer. However, a few amendments were needed and the process of re-submitting the research form went on for four weeks. This has caused a big portion of our time as we only had two weeks left until the day of submission. Contrarily, on the day we sent the final sets of questions and form, the faculty board has made a decision as an interim measure that primary data collection will only be permissible for undergraduates and Masters by Research programmes. Succeedingly, our lecturer changed the approach to a systematic literature review. Regretfully, this has again affected our progress as we had to restructure the whole project from the beginning.

With two weeks left to the deadline, my team and I tried to gather as much halal education, training and development related articles as possible. According to Mallet, Hagen-Zanker, Slater and Duvenzack (2012), one crucial condition for a systematic literature review is accessibility to an extensive range of databases. However, due to restricted access to various databases, some relevant articles were not included. Additionally, due to the exhaustive and time-consuming nature of a systematic literature review paper in regards to the high number of studies to be evaluated during the first stage of screening, more time is required to compile enough and useful data to make a conclusion on a specific topic. Despite the unwanted disruption during earlier stages, this particular project has made me learn about the importance of Halal education and training for the development of Halal industry. However, issues such as lack of human capital and inconsistencies of Halal standards as well as nonexistent key logistic infrastructures have posed a threat to the development of the industry. Sadly, for this assignment, i feel that the quality of the work we handed in could have been better and well supported if we were to be given more than just two weeks to do the systematic literature review.

Outcome of the module

After finishing one semester of the management course, I personally feel like I am going in the right path towards my main goal for pursuing this Master degree and I do believe what I learned from this is important for people that dream to pursue a career in this field. For this module particularly, I was hoping to learn more about Organizational Behaviour (OB), the

structure, processes and team management yet we barely had any classes, lectures or helpful guidelines and rather just given a textbook to read. Although the textbook contains all of the information needed but it does not equal effective teaching and learning. As cited by Bradshaw (2014), Rosetti and Fox mentioned four important categories for teaching success:

1. Teacher's presence and having a good respectful relationship with the students
2. Showing interest in student's understanding and what they have learned from the module
3. Continuously learning to update teaching strategies and module's syllabus
4. Passionate in the module and teaching of the module itself

In addition, Bradshaw also continued stating that despite the setting, be it in a physical classroom or a virtual one, the applicability of these four aspects still ring true. All in all, looking back throughout the four months of taking this module, it is quite dismal to see that we did not have a proper class or lecture on learning about OB and instead classes were just turned into a consultation time for research projects and IA. I was disappointed as I was pretty enthusiastic and excited to learn about the module and I feel it is one of the important subjects to learn in management. Lastly, I believe that this module could have been taught better with the consideration of Bradshaw's work on teaching success.

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